

Governance, Law and the Harm Principle: A Millian Exploration

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Abstract

This paper explores the interrelationship between governance, law, and the Harm Principle as articulated by John Stuart Mill in his seminal work, *On Liberty*. Mill's Harm Principle offers a compelling normative framework for evaluating legal and political authority. The paper critically examines how the principle can influence contemporary governance and legal systems, particularly in liberal democracies. The Harm Principle simply states that the liberty of an individual should only be restricted if it threatens to bring harm to other members of the society. This raises critical problem as regards the functions of law and governance in preserving common good without truncating individual rights. The paper acknowledges the convolutions and complications arising from explaining and appraising harm as well as the consequences thereof. It analyses the context within which the concept of harm can be discussed; recognizes the current global situation where technological inventions, evolution in culture, as well as a shift in the perception of the idea of harm constitute a challenge to the apparatus of law and governance. The paper contributes to the burgeoning conversation regarding the delicate task of striking an equilibrium between the libertarian conception of individual rights and ensuring that the people are protected as a collective, thus, suggesting ways through which law and governance can be modified and adjusted for the handling of human and societal existential quandaries in the light of present day realities. The paper further evaluates the harm principle and its prospects in steering policies in law and governance, as well as stimulates more critical perspectives for preserving personal liberty while safeguarding the welfare of the society at

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large. Ultimately, the paper contends that a Millian approach to governance and law, one rooted in the Harm Principle, offers a principled yet flexible guide for balancing individual rights with the legitimate interests of the state in a pluralistic society.

Keywords: Mill, Governance, Law, Harm Principle, rights, Liberty.

Introduction

Human beings by nature, yearn for peace and happiness. However, this cannot be realised in an atmosphere of disorder and lawlessness. A situation where there are hostilities and severe disagreements will most likely result into a condition similar to that of the Hobbesian state of nature, where life is said to be solitary, poor, nasty, brutish and short. To avert this ugly condition, the formation of a civil society became germane where there would be a government to preserve the law made by the people in accordance with the people's individual rights. The essence of government, thus, is to preserve and enforce laws for the welfare of the people. The people in a democratic system determine what laws to be made and how they will govern themselves while respecting their individual rights. However, tension often arises between individual liberty and the collective good.

The modern liberal democratic state grapples with this enduring tension. At the heart of this debate lies the question: When is it justifiable for the state to restrict individual freedoms? John Stuart Mill, in his seminal work *On Liberty* (1859), proposed the "harm principle" as a foundational criterion for such restrictions. Mill argues that there should be no restrictions to the liberty of individuals except to prevent harm. Mill's harm principle holds that only actions that directly bring harm to other members of the society should be justifiably restricted by the law, otherwise, every individual ought to be allowed to freely engage his or her liberty in search of happiness.

This paper aims at exploring the interrelationship between governance, law, and the Harm Principle as articulated by John Stuart Mill. It takes a cursory look at the role of the state in governance and preservation of law; examines Mill's Harm Principle as a foundation for individual liberty; and considers the implications of the Harm Principle for social order.

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Governance and law are basic phenomena that are inseparable for the purpose of piloting the affairs of human societies. The concept of the rule of law plays a pivotal role for the realisation of good governance as the state discharges its duties using the instrumentality of the law. Clearly, the law is a crucial framework for the enforcement of orderliness and the propagation of propriety within the state. The import of the above, according to Kaplan (2022: 622) is that, “all citizens, institutions, as well as government officials are answerable to the law”. In other words, there is no any single individual that is above the state and its laws.

As regards man and the state, Skowronski, following Aristotle, remarks that “the good is the same for an individual as for a city” (2017: 343). The import of the above is that, if the state is structured and administered in line with the principles of justice and fairness, it will trickle down to the citizens. One major political statement that has endured through ages and has gained much currency is the Aristotelian notion that the “essence of the state is for the creation of the good life, as there is no good human life outside of a state” (quoted in Nieswandt, 2025: 1). This assertion remains evergreen as it cuts across all eras of humanity. The idea of the good life here, is simply to protect the people from discomfort and ensure their wellbeing in the best possible ways.

The state is saddled with the duties of enforcing laws, ensuring accountability and protecting the rights of its citizens. The idea of safeguarding fundamental human rights has resonated in various ways and through several media as fundamental human rights are considered intrinsic to all beings no-matter their ethnicity, gender, social status or qualifications. As a matter of fact, the issue of human rights became more crucial and critical immediately after the Second World War. “These rights include the right to life, liberty, and security of person; freedom from torture and cruel treatment; equality before the law; and protection from discrimination” (UNHR 1948).

There is a responsibility on the part of the government to practically provide acts of governance. This is done following processes already enshrined in the constitution. The real candor and verity of law is the fact that every good law ought to have morality as its cornerstone. It is on this basis that human rights are considered “inviolable, imprescriptible, and inalienable” (Igwe, 2015: 380). They do not depend on any culture or human law or government. Unfortunately, these rights have been violated by states and individuals in various ways. Given the indispensable nature of these fundamental rights, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948) and many other global pacts and concordat strongly stress the need to proselytize and propagate them. It, therefore, behooves on states and institutions around the world to demonstrate the responsibility

of defending these rights, as well as guaranteeing the dignity and welfare of all citizens. This is the essence of governments and laws within the state.

Mill's Harm Principle: A Foundation for Individual Liberty

Mill's harm principle is deeply rooted in the liberal tradition, which emphasizes individual autonomy, reason, and the protection of personal liberty against coercive authority. Mill's utilitarian background, predicated on the ethical theory that actions are right if they promote the greatest happiness formulate s the harm principle not merely as a defense of freedom but as a utilitarian tool to maximize overall well-being by minimizing unnecessary interference.

Within the conceptual composition of Mill, harm constitutes any action or conduct that contravenes the rights of other members of the society. Harm in this case could be any form of distress ranging from physical, economic, social to emotional or any infractions of personal interests. Folland (2025) notes that "harm is normatively important and useful for philosophical theorizing". It is important because concerns the morality of people's actions against their fellow humans which are inimical to their well-being. As a proponent of the view that man is free to create, propagate and enjoy his own happiness, Mill envisaged the possibility of man's happiness being truncated by his fellow men. Accordingly, he considers the harm principle as the hub around which human actions are framed, and ultimately the framework that can regulate individual liberty.

In Mill's words, "the only purpose for which power can be rightfully exercised over any member of a civilized community, against his will, is to prevent harm to others" (2). This famous quotation is the central theme of what Mill referred to as the Harm Principle. The Harm Principle is a central cannon of the socio-political philosophy popularly referred to as liberalism which places emphasis on individual rights and personal liberty.

This principle simply holds that individuals should be allowed to exhibit the liberty of acting at their own discretion except unless their actions brings harm to another. Mill therefore, saw liberty as justifying the freewill of man as against the unlimited governmental powers and social control. He argued that happiness can be increased and sustained in human societies if good attempts are made to effectuate diversity, as well as allow the propagation of individual freedom. While citizens remain answerable to their government when their actions potentially or actually harm others.

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The kernel of Mill's principle is that it is a violation of human right to restrict an individual, if the actions of the individual does not in any way threaten other people's welfare. According to Mill "in the part which merely concerns himself, his independence is, of right, absolute. Over himself, over his own body and mind, the individual is sovereign" (1975: 2). In other words, an individual's actions, whether they be considered inane, half-witted, injudicious or unintelligent by others, the actor reserves the right to exercise his freewill and relate with others without interference, provided it does not cause harm to others. The harm principle may be explained thus: "Your right to swing your fist terminates where my nose begins." That is to say, individuals should be allowed the freedom to act and conduct themselves according to their wishes insofar as their freedom and actions do not impede the well-being of others or bring injury to them. However, if the liberties and rights of a man potentially bring harm to others, then the state can interfere by legally and rightfully going against the will of such individual.

The Harm Principle and Social Order

The social order could experience some form of imbalance if man were to be restricted and not allowed to exercise his liberty. Individual liberty, therefore, is a major requisite for the dignity and thriving of man. This idea of individual liberty according to Mill, is predicated on his principle of harm where persons should be allowed to chase their preferences and dreams, insofar as they do not bring harm to other citizens of the state. For Mill, the unique nature of every individual puts him/her in the best position to be the judge of his/her personal conditions, and determine his/her own happiness. He argues that the good life for Mr. "A" may not necessarily appeal to Mr. "B". Thus, Mill believes that everyone should be allowed to freely determine their own distinctive impression of the good life.

The harm principle as propagated by Mill does not support anarchical system, or call for the disbandment of socio-legal machineries. It rather proposes a model by which governance and law can be used for the strengthening of individual discretions and also preserve social order. Within this model, laws can help protect the rights of others from being violated, while allowing some level of individualistic freedom to the citizenry.

The crux of Mill's proposition is the ability to decipher between actions and behaviours that cause harm to others and some other action that merely offend others. That is to say, a law that helps avoid murder, rape or theft are absolutely justified in Mill's model because it clearly prevents harm from befalling a member of the society. But the regulation of a criticism of a

politician by a citizen is a complicated matter. To this end, Mill argues that “the state must carefully run checks to ascertain if regulating this really prevent harm or if it unnecessarily hampers an individual’s freedom of expression” (1975: 26).

The import of Mill’s idea in relation to social order is that there may be no need to attempt to fix what is not broken. He opines therefore, that governance ought to be characterised by very limited restrictions. This simply means not the absence of laws but the careful application of it in order to shield the public from harm rather than attempting to register a moral code. Mill’s principle simply requests for a legal society within which the government plays a role of an unbiased judge who protects people from harm when required while granting considerable liberty to individuals in the state.

During Mill’s time, the authorities promulgated laws that regulated some very personal behavior and conducts that in Mill’s opinion did not constitute harm to the public. Thus, Mill’s concept of individual liberty can be considered to be a reaction to the paternalistic attitude that inundated the European political ambience. His Harm Principle is therefore, a model intentionally structured with reasonable tolerance as its central theme. It gives an individual the opportunity to freely explore, hold different opinion, exhibit lifestyles of choice, all within the ambit of the law so long as they do not impinge on the rights of other citizens or create social disorderliness.

Evaluation

Mill exuded commendable astuteness in his harm principle which offers a strong defense of personal liberty, striking a significant balance between individual autonomy and social responsibility. Mill, in his theory, offers a moral and legal framework that promotes tolerance, diversity, and minimal state interference, which are ideals fundamental to a free and just society. Mill’s theory resonated with many scholars and has continued to make considerable impact till date. Undoubtedly, Mill was one of the most influential philosophers of the 19th century whose influence is still felt today.

Nonetheless, as compelling and strong as Mill’s theory has proven to be, the Harm Principle has been criticized. Critics continue to question what exactly constitutes harm in Mill’s view. The major challenge associated with this principle is the subjective nature of the concept of ‘Harm’. Critics point out that Mill did not clearly define what constitutes "harm." Is psychological offense harm? What about economic disadvantage or cultural erosion? The concept is vague and so, open to subjective interpretation.

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Several scholars, guilds, associations and societies may have diverse perceptions and reasoning regarding what constitutes harm, which may not align with other people's perceptions or views. Again, the harm principle does not necessarily align with the principle of law. For example, there may be situations of indirect harm, and in these cases, the law may be unable to differentiate personal acts that are permissible from those that should be censored for the safety of the public. It is in this regard that Feinberg (1984: 67) notes: "the Harm Principle cannot seem to adequately resolve cases where the harm to others is indirect or uncertain". The determinant of what constitutes harm, therefore, seems to vary and largely depends on several factors including economic, social, cultural and personal, and this presents a stumbling block to establishing clear legal territories. Feinberg (1984) upholds this view as he contends: "different personalities and groups may explain harm in different ways, which raises concerns about objectivity and consistency of the legal systems when applying the Harm Principle" (67).

Another argument against Mill's Harm Principle is that it does not convincingly address the problem of self-harm. This is a case where the actions of an individual bring harm to that individual. In such a case, should the government intervene when a person engages in nefarious acts like smoking and abuse of illegal substances? What about "cases of organ sale, assisted suicide, and consensual cannibalism"? (Igwe, 2015: 253). In approaching this challenge, Mill appeared to be double-faced. He admitted that a case of self-harm could be critical but that the government should only wade in on very special occasions depending on the severity of the case. How do we determine a severe case? Who should determine it? This is crucial as Mill had laid much emphasis on individual autonomy and right. Mill's principle is further accused of neglect of Indirect Harms. A lot of actions have ripple effects. For example, gambling or drug abuse may not directly harm others but can indirectly affect families or society. The line between self- and other-regarding actions, thus, is often blurry.

Stewart further stresses the challenges associated with the harm principle when he raised the issue of "core cases of criminal wrongdoing that can occur without causing any direct harm" (17). Folland on his part, argues that the "Harm Principle is plausible only if there is a full-blown, and problem-free, account of harm which proponents of the principle can refer to" (2022: 139). However, Baker identifies an advantage of the Harm Principle when he opined that "wrongful harm to others provides the only moral and constitutional justification for sending people to jail" (2008: 3). These underscore the debates that have risen from the Harm Principle.

Again, some critics believe that it is not all individuals that are capable of making rational and correct decisions at all times. Even if all were able to make rational decisions, critics contend that the responsibility of the society and its legal apparatuses go far beyond prevention of harm. It covers wider social injustices and unfairness that may impede individual liberty including: illiteracy, penury and different forms of discrimination. While the Harm Principle may be a veritable tool for individual liberty, many thinkers note that care must be taken during application: how to determine what harm is, as well as when the government should get involved to avert harm.

Mill's idea is quite estimable, in spite of the volumes of criticisms levelled against it. Truly, pessimists could sometimes be as important as the optimist, if not more important. It may take an optimist to conceive and create a plane, but it takes a pessimist's criticism for there to be safety measures, such as the manufacture and use of parachutes. Accommodating scholars and individuals with different perspectives and views, therefore, makes the phenomenon of life itself worthwhile. In spite of the criticisms against Mill's harm principle, our view is that insofar as an action is carried out within the ambit of rationality and within the confines of the law, Mill's idea remains a veritable framework for a better human society.

Conclusion

John Stuart Mill's harm principle remains a significant cornerstone of liberal thought, offering a sturdy framework for limiting state coercion and protecting individual freedom. Nonetheless, its practical application requires clarification of "harm" and acknowledgement of exceptions, particularly, in modern, interconnected societies. The appropriateness of Mill's Harm Principle may be a bit difficult to ascertain, especially, as regards establishing what exactly constitutes harm and how to handle indirect harms. As this paper has shown, the application of the harm principle in governance and law is fraught with complexity. Modern societies must contend with ambiguous, diffuse, and systemic forms of harm that challenge Mill's original distinctions.

While the harm principle should remain a central reference point, it must be interpreted in light of contemporary realities. Mill's idea can be critical to the curtailment of excessive administrative and bureaucratic powers, while protecting individuals in a legal arrangement. Governance and law should be structured to protect individual rights and create equilibrium while being conducted with impartiality for the welfare of all. Mill's principle, thus, constitutes a pattern for exercising legal authority in a liberal social order.

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